

Economic analysis of different electric propulsion technologies applied to last mile delivery fleet van composition.

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Highlights

- Adapted fleet replacement optimization model based on a mixed-integer linear programming (MILP).
- The lack of public suitable energy supply infrastructures for electric powered vans in Spain have been taken into account considering at depot refueling or recharging points.
- Electric drive technologies are compared with CNG powered vans, the most widely used low-emission alternative in Spain.
- Results reveal the feasibility of FC-EREV vans in UFT under certain operational conditions and fleet operator requirements, making possible to overcome range and infrastructure limitations in UFT in an economic optimal way.

Abstract

Sustainability, energy efficiency and cost optimization issues in logistic operations are more connected than ever before. Freight transport companies are facing new challenges, and urban distribution of goods plays a key role. In this sense, the use of electric vans will allow reaching the sustainability targets in an economic way. At present, almost all the electric powertrain technologies employed for light duty vehicles are based on battery electric vehicles (BEVs) but, in the near future, other electric powertrain configurations will be available. Hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FCEVs) and range extender hybrid electric/hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FC-EREVs) can play a key role in urban freight transport (UFT) activities. Depending on the powertrain typology, electric vans presents operational limitations, related to range, recharging time, recharging/refueling infrastructure and the lack of experience on the reliability of their powertrain, performance or economic feasibility. These uncertainties have been the motivation of the present investigation. Developing an adapted fleet replacement optimization model relying on a mixed integer linear programming (MILP) algorithm it is possible to determine the most suitable electric van from an economic point of view, depending on the fleet operational conditions and infrastructure requirements.

Electric drive vans are compared with natural gas powered vans (CNG), which are the most widely used low-emission alternative in Spain. The results indicate that FC-EREV vans are the most suitable option in a wide range of annual driving distances, ownership periods and fleet sizes. Under these conditions, on-site hydrogen production via electrolysis and using grid electricity could be an option to limited yearly distances (up to 25.000 km/year) and hydrogen purchase costs over 4,2 €/kg considering reference values for economic variables. Additionally, a sensitive and a breakeven analysis are conducted for assessing the effect of the model variables considered on the fleet per kilometer cost.

Keywords: electric van; fuel cell; range extender; urban freight transport; ownership cost; fleet replacement problem.

Nomenclature:

BEV	Battery electric van	HEV	Hybrid Electric Vehicle
BMS	Battery management system	HRS	Hydrogen refueling station
CD	Battery charge depleting mode	LCV	Light commercial vehicle
CS	Battery charge sustaining mode	LEZ	Low emission zones
DOE	Energy Department of EE.UU	MILP	Mixed-integer linear programming
EEA	European Environment Agency	PCU	Precooling unit
ESS	Energy storage system	PEM	Polymer electrolyte membrane
EU	European Union	UFT	Urban Freight Transport
EV	Electric vans	SME	Small and medium-sized enterprises
EVSE	Electrical vehicle supply equipment	SoC	Battery state of charge
FCEV	Fuel cell electric van	TCO	Total cost of ownership
FC-EREV	Fuel cell extended range electric van	TDCO	Total discounted cost of ownership
GHG	Greenhouse gas	TSP	Travelling salesman problem
GVW	Gross vehicle weight		

INTRODUCTION

We live in an industrialized world, heavily dependent on fossil fuels. Currently in EU almost 77% of energy consumption (Eurostat, 2021) are covered by fossil fuels as oil, gas and coal, with an overwhelming worldwide demand after pandemic and the consequent spike in energy prices, the national governments all over the world at the recently held COP 26 conference (United Nations, 2021) are setting guidelines for reducing global carbon emissions to be zero by 2050, a goal in which transportation plays an important role.

In this sense, the ecological transition and sustainability have gained worldwide relevance in the last years for national governments with the massive wave of climate change laws and standards, becoming key aspects of the future economic development. The Spanish Government, under European Union (EU) climate legislation and policies context, has developed different laws (Congreso de los Diputados XIV Legislatura, 2020) to build the institutional and regulatory framework to reach decarbonization target of the Spanish economy by 2050. These Spanish Government measures will drive the green energy transition based on: (i) the renewable electricity generation, (ii) taking actions to minimize the use of energy from fossil fuels, (iii) developing the use of renewable fuels that fulfill the EU sustainability regulations, and (iv) a challenge for a sustainable transport and mobility, in this sense, specific attention is paid to light vehicle fleet, basically composed of passenger cars and commercial vans or light trucks. In fact in Spain, the carriage of goods by road is responsible for the bulk of emissions of more than 83 million tons CO₂ in 2018 (Observatorio del Transporte y la Logística en España, 2020) and almost 34% corresponds to urban haulage. In fact, the EU road transport emissions coming from light commercial vehicles

(LCV) are growing in the recent years due to there are an increasing quantity of vans on the road, higher distances travelled, low efficiency powertrains and a weak regulation in terms of CO₂ emissions, which is currently set in 147 g CO₂/km (Van Bokhorst et al., 2017). To reverse this trend, in 2019 a new EU regulation (European Parliament, 2019) fixed a target emission level reduction by 2030 of 31% compared to 2021 levels in accordance with the future EU regulatory framework for new registrations of passenger cars and light commercial vehicles (European Commission, 2021). That will establish a final target of zero emissions as it is detailed in the 2050 Spanish long-term strategy (European Commission, 2020). Nevertheless, actual emissions levels remain stable from 2019 at 158 g CO₂/km level (European Environment Agency, 2021).

In addition to greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, road transport is also a large energy consumer. In Spain, this corresponds to more than 36% of the overall energy demand, and it almost entirely comes from fossil fuels. Therefore it should be a priority sector to be decarbonized. To this effect, it is necessary to adopt measures promoting the penetration of green vehicles adapted to the society demand and deployment of the necessary infrastructure.

Under this context, freight transport companies are actively promoting sustainable measures for the logistics activities trying to improve the energetic efficiency and to reduce their carbon footprint with lower cost per covered kilometer (Lean & Green, 2022). Sustainable logistic focuses on, amongst others measures, the renewal of the vehicle fleet and storage systems, promote of digitalization and digital technologies, increase the delivery chain efficiency and promote the use of territorial production and distribution centers that serve as reference points for a given geographic zone. However, distribution of goods in metropolitan areas faces additional challenges for freight transport companies. The urban freight transport (UFT) is focused on carrying goods to the end consumer using commercial vehicles and these operations are complex because while they involve a lot of actors, heterogeneous loads (typologies, sizes and weights), shortening of delivery times, several hand-over points with time restrictions and multiple distance requirements to be covered. At present, UFT demand services are increasing mostly due to the increasing growth of urban population (EEA, 2019), urban land take (Reichel et al., 2018) and the widespread use of e-commerce services. Additionally, local authorities are introducing low emission zones (LEZs) and tightening emission limits. In this respect, the type of vehicles composing the delivery fleet for UFT is a key part. The progressive substitution of conventional internal combustion vans by electric models will allow reaching the sustainability targets, if the electricity comes from renewable sources. But in this regard there is still a long way to go too, as currently, in EU less than 30% of energy needed (Eurostat, 2021) proceed from renewable sources, although it is expected to increase to 40% by 2030 (Global Data, 2021).

However, it should be noted that nowadays in the Spanish energy mix the percentage of renewable energy sources are over 43% (Red Electrica de España, 2021). At present, almost all the electric powertrain technologies employed for light duty vehicles are based on battery electric vehicles (BEVs) but, in the near future, they will be available to find other electric powertrain configurations: hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FCEVs) and range extender hybrid electric/hydrogen fuel cell vehicles (FC-EREVs), that would be interesting for UFT activities (Castillo et al., 2020). To a greater or lesser extent, electric vans have operational limitations, such as the real useful range in operating conditions and the battery recharging time. The scarce public recharging infrastructures and the unavailability of hydrogen refueling stations are other operational restrictions that have been considered. In addition, the lack of experience in their powertrain reliability and performance, uncertain financial viability due to the high purchase costs, unknown operational costs and resale value are also to be taken into account. These issues could be

important barriers in the short term adoption (Watróbski et al., 2017; Castillo et al., 2020). In the long run, many of identified problems in electric powertrain technologies are expected to decrease or disappear as a result of mass production. Until then, the freight transport companies must take now operational decisions with a strategic point of view. Technical and economic benefits of electric vans (EV) versus conventional internal combustion engines depends on several parameters, namely: (i) total cost of ownership (TCO), (ii) powertrain characteristics, such as battery size, charging or refueling capacity, real energy consumption and component service life, and (iii) charging or refueling infrastructure costs (Schücking and Jochem, 2021).

Therefore, the optimization of commercial vehicle fleets based on electric drives which satisfies particular operator requirements is becoming a key challenge. EV should be a better option for commercial fleet operations not only in terms of environmental aspects but also regarding to operation costs. It is for this reason that the main objective of this investigation is to assess the economic viability of different van fleet composition, with particular emphasis in FC-EREV vehicles, considering their economic aspects, operational limitations and performances in urban delivery work conditions. Specially, our comprehensive and comparative calculations for different EVs provide economic information regarding to capital and operational costs associated to the vehicles and its necessary recharging or refueling infrastructure under different scenarios that include economic, vehicular and infrastructure parameters, operational conditions and fleet operator requirements. Therefore, it is possible to provide an analysis tool to guide the solution for fleet replacement problem.

The research work has been organized as follows. First section illustrates a review of the available literature related to fleet composition problem for commercial vehicles and an overview of the Spanish van market. The second section explains the assumptions, optimization methodology and data used in the research. The third section shows the results and conclusions obtained in the sensitivity and breakeven analysis carried out on the scenarios considered. Finally, it is presented the main findings and future research paths.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This section deals with the literature background related to the models used to solve fleet composition problems with three different objectives: supporting fleet management decisions and forecasting vehicle type and optimal powertrain technology portfolio. Hereafter is presented an overview of the actual Spanish van market.

Fleet composition problems

In the literature, the aspects of this research are framed and commonly included within the topic fleet composition problems. They generally use models that support the decision-making process in fleet management activities. The problems addressed by the documents analyzed can be broadly divided in three groups:

- Routing problem with mixed fleets (RMF). The objective of this type of problems based on the travelling salesman problem (TSP) is to determine the optimal route set providing tailored services to fit the customers' needs under time, distance or emissions restrictions.
- Fleet mix and sizing problem (FMS). This problem corresponds to determine the fleet vehicle number and its characteristics or a combination of both. The fleet sizing is the definition of the number of vehicles in the fleet to ensure the demand satisfaction. On the other hand, the fleet mix implies the selection of the vehicle characteristics, such as powertrain type, payload and volume capacity or

specific needs such as temperature-controlled transport of goods for example, more suitable to the fleet operator requirements.

- Fleet replacement problem (FR). The aim of fleet replacement problems is to determine the optimal replacement time schedule to perform the minimal fleet cost to the company in a certain time interval. It is important to note that the vans' performances will deteriorate with the usage and age, and this issue will affect to powertrain efficiency, operational, maintenance and repair cost, imposing a replacement to avoid increments in costs.

Optimization models in fleet composition studies have not been only used for management purposes, but also for forecasting vehicle type diffusion (Mulholland et al., 2016) and optimal powertrain technology portfolio (Kellner et al., 2021). These studies have different stakeholders than fleet operators, such as governments for policy and regulation planning purposes, and vehicle manufacturers with the aim for adapting to new market conditions.

Up to the moment, the studies that addressed the economic optimization focused on commercial fleets considering vehicle technical features, infrastructure concerns and different powertrain configurations are scarce. The documents analyzed have several problem characteristics, parameters, constraints, settings and solution methods. However, the studied models try to optimize a fitness function based on economic aspects and/or environmental concerns (such as total cost of ownership and CO₂ emissions), using vehicular technical features (basically, energy consumption, battery aging and among others) and taking into account infrastructure issues (such as investment cost or charging opportunity) and working conditions. In the latter case, distance demand or restricted access to low emission zones are used as constraints, and additionally for BEV charging opportunity or downtime restrictions. Additionally, some studies have considered battery issues, such as aging and climate behavior. On the other hand, the methodology applied to solve the problem is usually based on deterministic modeling using a linear programming solver with a further scenario analysis in order to make a model sensitive check and to overcome the uncertainty limitations of the model parameters used. However, studies that use stochastic methodology considers explicitly distance demand, number of deliveries and/or energy price uncertainty. Table 1 summarizes an outlook of the problems, topics and powertrains addressed in the documents analyzed, while Table 2 resumes the methodologies applied to solve the optimization problem.

Table 1. Previous studies related to fleet composition: type of problems, topics and powertrain analyzed.

Problem Type			Analyzed topic				Powertrain				Ref.
FMS	RMF	FR	Economic aspects	Environment concerns	Vehicle technical features	Charging & refueling issues	ICE	BEV	FCEV	Others	
X			X	X	Basic		X	X			(Figliozzi et al., 2011)
X			X	X	Basic		X	X			(Feng and Figliozzi, 2013)
X			X		Advanced	X		X			(Schücking and Jochem, 2021)
X			X				X	X			(Pinto and Lagorio, 2021)
X				X	Basic		X	X			(Figliozzi et al., 2020)
X			X	X	Basic	X	X	X		X	(Lemme et al., 2019)
	X			X	Basic		X	X			(Islam and Gajpal, 2021)
X			X				X				(Li and Pan, 2018)
	X		X			X		X			(Hiermann et al., 2016)
X			X			X		X			(Lebeau et al., 2016)
		X	X				X				(Redmer, 2015)
	X		X		Basic	X	X	X			(Lebeau et al., 2015)
	X		X	X	Advanced		X				(Koç et al., 2014)
		X	X		Basic		X			X	(Parthanadee et al., 2012)
		X	X		Basic					X	(Redmer, 2020)
		X	X		Basic		X	X			(Ahani et al., 2016)
	X		X		Advanced			X			(Xiao et al., 2019)
	X		X	X	Advanced		X				(Shi et al., 2020)

Table captions: fleet mix and sizing problem (FMS), routing problem with mixed fleets (RMF) and fleet replacement problem (FR).

Table 2. Previous studies related to fleet composition problem: modeling type, solver, objective function and analysis methodology used.

Modeling type			Solver methodology	Objective function			Analysis				Ref.	
HM	DM	SM		TCO	MTCO	PC	LCA	SA	MSA	EA	RA	
	X		LP		X			X				(Figliozzi et al., 2011)
	X		LP		X			X		X		(Feng and Figliozzi, 2013)
		X	SBP			X			X			(Pinto and Lagorio, 2021)
	X		LP				X			X		(Figliozzi et al., 2020)
	X		LP	X				X				(Lemme et al., 2019)
X			MHP		X							(Islam and Gajpal, 2021)
		X	SBP		X							(Li and Pan, 2018)
X			LP		X							(Hiermann et al., 2016)
			CBC									(Lebeau et al., 2016)
	X		LP	X								(Redmer, 2015)
	X		LP	X								(Lebeau et al., 2015)
X			NLP	X								(Koç et al., 2014)
	X		LP	X								(Parthanadee et al., 2012)
X			LP	X								(Redmer, 2020)
	X		LP	X							X	(Ahani et al., 2016)

Table captions: heuristic modeling (HM), deterministic modeling (DM), stochastic modeling (SM), linear programming (LP), no-linear programming (NLP), stochastic based programming (SBP), meta-heuristic programming (MHP), choice-based conjoint (CBC), total cost of ownership (TCO), modified total cost of ownership (MTCO), life cycle analysis (LCA), scenario analysis (SA), multi-scenario analysis Monte Carlo (MSA), elasticity analysis (EA) and risk analysis (RA).

As it can be deduced from Table 1, most of the studies have paid low attention to other alternatives than BEV and no one has integrated an economic analysis of charging/refueling infrastructure investments for using electric or hydrogen vehicles in the fleet and did not rely on public infrastructure. In the near future, the possible alternatives in the market to replace the conventional vans will be varied, not only by battery electric powered vans, but also by hydrogen and hybrid electric/hydrogen vehicles. Conversely, in Table 2 it can be observed that the deterministic modeling type based on a cost objective function solved using a linear programming method is the preferred option to analyze fleet composition problems.

Van market characteristics in Spain

The commercial vehicle classification in Europe is based on UNECE standards (Unece, 2005). It is named N category and it comes in weight classes based on the gross vehicle weight (GVW). For metropolitan good deliveries, the most used vehicle is classified as light commercial vehicle (LCV) and it belongs to N1 category and GVW upper limit of 3,5 tones.

There is a wide variety models within the LCV – N1 category and a distinction is usually established among three van size classes (Van Bokhorst et al., 2017):

- Small vans: those vehicles that have an empty vehicle weight less than 1500 kg and a payload capacity less than 500 kg.
- Regular vans: vehicles that have an empty vehicle weight in the range 1500 – 2000 kg and a payload capacity from 500 kg to 1000 kg.
- Large vans: those vehicles that have an empty vehicle weight greater than 2000 kg and a payload over 1000 kg.

This classification may be slightly altered by the inclusion of electric vans due to the empty vehicle weight is greater than the conventional vans and the payload is reduced mainly due to the weight of batteries.

Along the following paragraphs we will make an overview of the Spanish market structure analyzing data related to the van market share, fleet composition and vehicle use in order to shed light on the trends in urban transportation vehicular requirements.

Van fleet composition and new van registrations annual evolutions in Spain since year 2011 with an upper GVW limit of 3,5 tones is showed in Figure 1a and Figure 1b with the size classification already explained according to data provided by Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020).

Figure 1a. Spanish van market share annual evolution. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020).

Figure 1b. Spanish share of new van registrations annual evolution. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020).

On the other hand, if we consider the age fleet composition, see Figure 2a and Figure 2b, the average age of the Spanish van fleet is quite old, with almost 50% of the fleet with more than 14 years. The van class longest-lived is the small size, followed by the regular size and in the last places it is the large class.

Figure 2a. Spanish van fleet composition by class and years of age. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020).

Figure 2b. Spanish van fleet composition distributed by age. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020).

The average annual mileage of the Spanish van fleet depends on the van age and size class (see Figure 3). The distance travelled by large vans is always higher than other classes regardless of the van age. The distance travelled by vans is decreasing as age increases. If we take as a reference the regular van size, it goes from 16.000 km to 22.000 km approximately. This disparity in mileage traveled by class and age of van results in, for instance, relatively modern vans with ages up to 4 years, which represent less than 18% runs through near 40% of the average distance travelled by the van fleet as is showed in Figure 4. Therefore, we can consider that the van average mileage is comprised between 16.000 km to 40.000 km.

Figure 3. Spanish van fleet annual mileage average distributed by age. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2018).

Figure 4. Spanish van fleet percentage of annual average distance travelled distributed by age related to total van fleet. Own elaboration based on data from Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2018).

Moreover, commercial vans have a wide range of applications. In Spain, vans are extensively used by small and medium-sized companies (SMEs) but there is no specific statistics that shows the van characteristics by application sector. However, if we take EU data as a reference, the vans that travel the longest distances are the ones related to good transport and storage activities (Van Bokhorst et al., 2017). On the other hand, according to data

provided by Spanish DGT (Dirección General de Tráfico, 2020), more than 83% of the fleet are diesel vans and less than 1% uses other fuels. In this share, only 33% are electric vehicles.

As it can be deduced from the data provided, the regular van size is the most preferred option with an average annual mileage comprised between 16.000 km to 40.000 km and with less than 14 years old. Furthermore, electric vehicles are not considered as alternative to diesel powered vans mainly due to high purchase costs, operational challenges, the lack of available fueling/charging infrastructures and uncertainty along time around vehicle performances, costs and adaptability for different usage patterns (Van Bokhorst et al., 2017).

METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this study is to find the optimal economic renewal of the commercial fleet with electric vehicles taking into account its particular energy supply infrastructure compared to an alternative solution currently in use such as gas-powered vehicles. With this aim, the authors have proposed a simulation tool that gives the optimal economic solution to a fleet composition problem, considering replacement concerns, ownership period, number of vans in the fleet, acquisition, maintenance and energy costs, and several distance demand estimations and infrastructure requirements, using a single objective deterministic linear programming methodology. Subsequently, a multiple scenario approach with a sensitivity and breakeven analysis has been used to establish the influence of the model parameters and economic variables on the model results in a large time horizon.

The first part of this section is dedicated to the assumptions made with regard to the fleet operator requirements and the vehicle and energy supply infrastructure characteristics considered to build the model. The ownership cost structure designed is explained below and finally, it is exposed the model formulation followed by the data used in the model.

Underlying model assumptions.

Fleet operator requirements.

At present, due to the scarce public recharging infrastructure and the lack of first HRS infrastructures, the presented model considers the adequate energy supply infrastructure to be installed at the depot. The fleet operators have to bear these added costs. In this sense, the van driving range should be sufficient to complete the working hours. In the case of BEV is considered that the van is only ready for charging at the end of the day when parking on the distribution center, this also avoids the use of DC fast charging stations and uncertainty in recharge time because the battery management system (BMS). Nevertheless, for hydrogen powered vans this limitation does not exist and the refueling operation could be done at the change of work shift for example if it is necessary.

The demand transportation satisfaction will depend on the number and type of vehicles. In the model it is assumed that the number and capacity of vans in the fleet is such that it satisfies the expected demand. This means that if the demand has a value close to the overall fleet capacity, there will be no preference in the use of new versus older vans and the utilization ratio will be the same in all the vans.

On the other hand, the transportation scheme used is the classical distribution model one-to-many, where the delivery route starts at a distribution center and delivers goods to different customers, and finishes again at the same distribution center. The van operating schedule will be 14 hours per day distributed in two shifts.

Additionally, the following assumptions with regard to the initial van fleet composition and the replacement rules have been taken into consideration in the model:

- Starting time of analysis all the vehicles in the fleet company are ICE-CNG vans with ages uniformly distributed from age 0 to the ownership period considered in each scenario.
- Only new vans will be purchased. Despite replacing vans with brand-new ones is not the economic best practice, the consideration of leading-edge powertrain technology hampers the use of second-hand vans (Parthanadee et al., 2012).

Van characteristics.

The study aims to show the technical and cost trade-offs associated to three electric technologies (BEV, FCEV and FC-EREV), comparing them to a currently used green van powertrain option such as ICE-CNG using current van models available in the Spanish market. The van model type used belongs to the Stellantis group, which leads the light commercial vehicles (LCV) market in EU during 2020 with more than 34% of market share (Statista, 2022).

As explained in Spanish van market section the regular van size is the preferred option, therefore the models selected belong to this category. The electrified vans are based on vans build up over standard mid-van platform developed by Stellantis group companies, such as Peugeot e-Expert, Citroën ë-Jumpy, Opel Vivaro-e or Fiat E-Scudo. The BEV model selected includes a 75 kWh battery in order to get a driving range similar to the fuel cell options and to avoid range anxiety due to cold weather, unexpected working conditions or battery aging. Moreover, for the CNG option it has been selected a Fiat Ducato L1H1.

The Stellantis group has recently introduced electric vans using the same platform with hydrogen fuel cell, becoming the first vehicle brand manufacturer to put hydrogen powered LCV on the road. Nevertheless, the Stellantis powertrain configuration is similar to a full FCEV not a FC-EREV. The electrified hydrogen van includes a polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM) fuel cell with 45 kW as the main power source supported with a 10,5 kWh Li-ion plug-in battery to cover peak loads, while the power plant is the same electric motor with 100 kW as the electric version already available. This configuration ensures a range of more than 400 km with 4,4 kg of hydrogen in accordance to company specified preliminary range using the WLTP test procedure. Therefore, this powertrain setting is similar to a FCEV using a more powerful plug-in battery to ensure that the fuel cell system always works under optimal conditions and the PEM fuel cell stack is sized to meet the maximum power output of the van traction electric motor while the battery would cover peak transient energy demands and recover kinetic energy, apart from saving the excess energy delivered by the fuel cell stack.

However, the FC-EREV approach is basically a battery vehicle, which includes a small PEM fuel cell stack as generator to extend the driving range charging and keeping the Li-ion battery at its best efficiency conditions. This powertrain configuration but with a petrol engine generator can be found for example in the recently discontinued BMW i3 REX which uses a 28 kW engine to increase the range provided by the 33 kWh capacity battery (InsideEVs, 2019). At the present time, a similar extender range concept is available in the Ford Transit Plug-In Hybrid but with a more powerful petrol engine generator of 92 kW and a battery capacity of 14 kWh. Also, in the near future it will be available the Renault Master H2-TECH with a 30 kW PEM fuel cell stack generator and a battery achieving 33 kWh capacity (Hyvia, 2022).

The selection of powertrain components for the fuel cell powered electric vans is based on the currently available on the market fuel cell vehicles. Table 3 shows an overview of the technical specifications of all the van options used in the study (Pagerit et al., 2006; Electrification Coalition, 2010; Kurtz et al., 2017; Kleiner and Friedrich, 2017a; Trost et al., 2017; Thompson et al., 2018; Contact et al., 2018; Giordano et al., 2018; Kurtz et al., 2019; Tikhomirov et al., 2019; Preger et al., 2020; Rechkemmer et al., 2020; Krause et al., 2020; Handwerker et al., 2021).

Table 3. Van characteristics.

	Unit	CNG	BEV	FC-EREV	FCEV	Notes
ICE power	(kW)	101,4	-	-	-	(1)
FC system power	(kW)	-	-	30	100	
Electric motor power	(kW)	-	100	100	100	(2)
Storage capacity - NG	(kg)	36	-	-	-	(3)
Storage capacity - H2	(kg)	-	-	1,5	3	
Battery nameplate capacity	(kWh)	-	75	28	2	(2)
Battery CD mode used	(%)	-	0,8	0,8	0,45	(4)
Usable battery energy	(kWh)	-	60	22	0,9	
AC charge power (low)	(kW)	-	-	7,4	-	(5)
AC charge power (high)	(kW)	-	11	-	-	(5)
Battery lifetime	(cycles)	-	2000	2400	3200	
FC stack lifetime	(h)	-	-	11900	3500	
Basic body weight	(kg)	1566	1576,4	1576,4	1576,4	(1) (2) (6)
Powertrain weight	(kg)	135	28,6	28,6	28,6	
FC stack and peripheral components weight	(kg)	-	-	25	60	(7)
Fuel tank weight	(kg)	194	-	26	53	(1) (7)
Battery pack weight	(kg)	-	483	180	12	(2)
Curb weight	(kg)	1895	2088	1811	1670	(1) (2)
NG consumption	(kg/100 km)	8,6	-	-	-	(1) (8)
H2 consumption	(kg/100 km)	-	-	0,93	1,16	
Electricity consumption	(Wh/km)	-	246,8	224,6	-	
H2 range	(km)	-	-	161,3	258	
Electricity range	(km)	-	243,1	99,7	-	(2) (8)
Useful range	(km)	418,6	243,1	261	258	

Table notes: (1) Based on Fiat Ducato L1H1 CNG (<https://www.fiatprofessional.com>); (2) Based on Peugeot Expert BEV Pro Standard (<https://www.peugeot.es/gama/expert-furgon.html>); (3) CNG density 158 kg/m³ (20 MPa - 15 °C); (4) For BEV and FC-EREV charge depleting mode considered is 10% to 90% of battery capacity, but in a FCEV charge depleting mode considered is 30% to 75%, a similar range is used in HEV; (5) Stellantis mid van electric on board charger usually assembled have 7,4 kW and 11 kW; (6) Basic body weight includes all the common components between vehicle configurations such as vehicle body and basic systems (steering wheel, suspension, brakes, wheels, etc.); (7) Fuel cell stack and balance of plant system weight based on Toyota Mirai technical specifications; (8) WLTP ratings for ICE and BEV vehicle configuration

The FCEV powertrain components are based in the Stellantis mid van battery model modified using Toyota Mirai data (Lohse-Busch and Stutenberg, 2018), considering hydrogen tank capacity in accordance with the BEV drives range. For the FC-EREV model is also built from Stellantis mid van battery model and the fuel cell system sizing powertrain components have taken into account the average power consumption in the WLTP class 2 and class 3 test procedures (Tikhomirov et al., 2019) and the most efficient fuel cell stack working range. The best fuel cell system efficiency is reached at 15 – 25% of its maximum power (Lohse-Busch and Stutenberg, 2018), thus if the average driving power required is around 5 to 8 kWh then the fuel cell stack power should be 30 kW approximately. This estimation is aligned with the generator power used in the above mentioned range extender vehicles. On the other hand, a 28 kWh battery nameplate capacity has been chosen to keep weight and cost in check by traveling the longest possible distance using the electrical energy stored in the battery. The hydrogen tank capacity is such that it allows having more or less the same autonomy as the BEV.

The average consumption fuel cell powered vans in a working day could be calculated through modeling simulations or real test data, nevertheless several parameters could affect the consumption in real drive conditions (number of stops, rate of accelerations, average speed, climate conditions, traffic state, rate of regenerative braking and so on). In this case, the hydrogen consumption estimation is made using a simulation framework already used in a recent work (Fernández and Pérez-Dávila, 2022).

The crucial factor for an electric van is the battery condition. The expected maximum battery capacity loss in over the lifetime is 20 - 30% of its initial value (Rechkemmer et al., 2020). Currently, automotive manufacturers can guarantee 2000 charging cycles (Electrification Coalition, 2010; Handwerker et al., 2021), which equals a vehicle operation of 8 years if the van is charged every day. Nevertheless, the battery lifetime is highly dependent on battery depth of discharge (DoD), limiting minimum and maximum battery charge level using the 20 – 80% rule will preserve the battery from premature degradation. However, it is expected that in the next few years it will be able to exceed the 5,000 charging cycles. In this sense, the future UNECE regulations will require manufacturers to guarantee a battery capacity loss of less than 20% to 30% of its original capacity during 5 years (100.000 km) and 8 years (160.000 km) respectively (Unece, 2021).

The PEM fuel cell stack lifetime is also a challenge. The Energy Department of United States (DOE) lab experiments shows a lifetime around 3000 – 6200 hours with continuous start up and shut down, however in continuous run the expected lifetime is significantly increased (Kurtz et al., 2017). On the other hand, the fuel cell vehicle manufacturers, such Toyota and Hyundai, provide a minimum powertrain warranty of 160.000 km (Hyundai, 2020).

Energy supply infrastructure characteristics.

At present, when companies acquire electric vans, due the shortage or absence of public energy supply infrastructure, it is necessary to adapt or install the adequate energy supply infrastructure providing sufficient electric power. In this sense, there are three possibilities: purchase energy from the grid, off-grid energy generation or a combination of both. For industrial facilities it is possible coupling an off-grid renewable electricity generation,

produced with solar panels for instance, with a buffer energy storage system (ESS) and the AC grid power supply connection using an inverter to fulfill the energy demand. In this study the authors have not considered local electricity generation, therefore all the electricity consumed comes from the grid. The following explains the configuration of the recharging and hydrogen refueling infrastructure at the distribution center adopted in this study for energy supply to the van fleet.

If we focus on the BEV recharging infrastructure, currently the more available charging infrastructure is the Mode 3 configuration with 11 – 22 kW of power output for 16A and 32A 400VaC installations. At present, the typical power output of on-board AC-DC transformer is in the range between 3,7 kW to 22 kW. The objective of the on-board charger is to use the readily available AC grid power managing single-phase and 3-phase charging stations. However, in case of DC fast chargers the battery management system (BMS) works without the use of the on-board charger and usually the vehicle could accept an input power over 50 kW. For further information, please refer to Appendix A.

In this study the authors have considered that the electricity consumed it is supplied by a 3-phase Mode 2 or 3 AC charger (380 – 440 V) with a power output up to 22 kW because are usually adopted for industrial installations. In this conditions, the usual charging efficiency is around 85% to 92 % (Electrification Coalition, 2010; Trentadue et al., 2018), that will be considered for grid electricity consumption. Table 4 summarizes the electricity supply components characteristics used in this study.

Table 4. Electricity supply characteristics.

	Units	Value
Electric slow charging efficiency	(%)	0,87
Charger for BEV		Mode 3 - 11 kW
Charger for FC-EREV		Mode 2 - 7,4 kW
Electric charging infrastructure lifetime	(years)	10

At the end of the year 2019 there were working over 400 public hydrogen refueling stations (HRS) around the world, most of them in Japan, US and EU, mainly in Germany (H2 Stations, 2021). As it can be noted, the time when fuel cell vehicles get a significant market share, and therefore a network of commercial filling stations, is still not clear. An alternative could be supplying hydrogen produced on-site through water electrolysis (Bartolozzi et al., 2013) with electric power coming from renewable sources. Other possible option could be to purchase hydrogen in high pressure cylinders up to 50 l (Linde, 2021) with vehicular fuel quality (ISO, 2019). The hydrogen is supplied into high-pressure cylinders (20 – 30 MPa as standard). In this sense, the adoption of an on-site hydrogen refueling infrastructure at the depot could improve the competitiveness of hydrogen powered delivery vans versus battery electric ones (Van Mierlo et al., 2006; Baptista et al., 2010).

Actually, there are a variety of technologies for HRS suitable for different scale levels of hydrogen demand. The hydrogen refueling infrastructure, irrespective of scale, comprises the following basic components: generation and storage of hydrogen, pressure refueling equipment and the dispenser. Figure 5 shows a representation of the hydrogen refueling station configuration used in this study.

Figure 5. Hydrogen refueling configurations.

There are three main types of electrolyzer technologies available in the market: polymer electrolyte membrane (PEM), alkaline and solid oxide. The electrolyzers with a solid oxide membrane electrolyte works at high temperatures (about 700°– 800°C) to function properly compared to commercial PEM and alkaline electrolyzers which have 70 – 90°C and 100 – 150°C operation temperatures respectively. Therefore, this type of electrolyzers is of interest if there is a nearby source of residual heat to reduce the electrical consumption for the water electrolysis. Therefore low temperature electrolyzers are the more adopted option for low-scale on-site hydrogen production.

In addition to the electrolyzer unit, it is required purification systems for water and hydrogen, and also a dryer unit to treat the hydrogen produced. The hydrogen is generated at relatively low pressure, 1 to 3 MPa and it is required a further downstream compression to elevate the pressure, typically at 80 or 90 MPa. Afterwards hydrogen is transferred to a compressed storage vessel. Finally, the dispenser delivers hydrogen into the vehicle's tank at 70 MPa. Due to the rapid recompression of the vehicle tank and the fueling nozzle it is necessary a precooling system to maintain the vehicle tank temperature between 50 – 60 °C and avoid exceeding 85°C according to SAE J2601 regulation (SAE, 2014) .

The electricity consumption is one of the key points in the hydrogen production by electrolysis. The main energy-consuming components are the electrolyzer, compressor and cooling system. Small scale PEM electrolyzers with a flow rate less than 2 kgH₂/h have an electricity consumption around 60 kWh per H₂ kilogram produced and medium scale electrolyzers up to 10 kgH₂/h have an electricity consumption around 56 kWh per H₂ kilogram (Tractebel et al., 2017; IRENA, 2018; Ligen et al., 2018; Handwerker et al., 2021; International Energy Agency, 2021). Currently, hydrogen compression energy consumption in HRS is around 3,1 kWh per H₂ kilogram to fill the storage reservoir to 88 MPa from the outlet electrolyzer pressure, typically 2 MPa (DOE, 2009; Brown et al., 2012; Ligen et al., 2018). The precooling unit (PCU) temperature should have to be kept around -40°C to reduce the temperature of the dispensed hydrogen into the van. Apart from PCU technical characteristics, the unit energy consumption depends on the dispensed hydrogen flow rate and the number of refueling per time unit. In the worst case when the refrigeration unit must to satisfy the cooling demand continuously the electricity energy consumption is around 1,4 – 1,9 kWh per H₂ kilogram dispensed at 70 MPa considering 2 kg H₂/min and 14°C of hydrogen flow rate and ambient temperature respectively (Brown et al., 2012; Elgowainy et al., 2017) . Additionally, it has been considered an electrical energy consumption of the remaining hydrogen infrastructure components of 2 kWh per H₂

kg if hydrogen is produced on-site and 0.8 kWh per H₂ kg if it is purchased in high pressure cylinders. In Table 5 it is summarized the characteristics of the hydrogen supply components used in this study (De Bruijn et al., 2008; DOE, 2009; Brown et al., 2012; DOE, 2014; Parks et al., 2014; Elgowainy et al., 2017; Kurtz et al., 2017; Tractebel et al., 2017; IRENA, 2018; Ligen et al., 2018; Ulleberg and Hancke, 2020; IRENA, 2020; Handwerker et al., 2021; IEA, 2021).

Table 5. Hydrogen supply components characteristics.

	Units	Value	Notes
Electrolyzer installed power (small scale production < 2 kgH ₂ /h)	(kW/Nm ³ H ₂)	5,6	(1)
Electrolyzer installed power (medium scale production < 10 kgH ₂ /h)	(kW/Nm ³ H ₂)	5.3	(1)
Electrolyzer Water consumption	(m ³ /kg H ₂)	0,0143	
Compressor installed power	(kW/Nm ³ H ₂)	0,1 – 0,31	(2)
Pre-cooling system	(kW)	8	(3)
Electrolyzer lifetime	(years)	10	(4)
Compressor lifetime	(years)	10	(5)
Dispenser flow rate	(kg/min)	2	(6)
Dispenser lifetime	(years)	8	
High pressure tanks lifetime	(years)	20	

Table notes: (1) Own assumption of electrolyzer installed electrical power based on commercially available PEM electrolyzers, (2) Own assumption of compressor installed electrical power based on commercially available models, the lower value is for compressors does not exceed an 8 to 1 compression ratio, (3) H₂ flow rate up to 2 kg/min 14 – 25°C H₂ starting temperature cooled to -40°C and uniformly refueling demand per hour, (4) Electrolyzer lifetime in stationary conditions 40.000 - 50.000 h, with an electrolyzer utilization rate of 0,7 and an average annual utilization of 4200 h, (5) Compressor expected lifetime more than 40.000 h with an average annual utilization of 4200 h, (6) Usual flow rate range from 0,5 to 5 kg/min.

Total fleet ownership cost.

The total fleet ownership cost (TCO) is a basic decision criterion. Previously, it is necessary to identify the key cost inputs that are important for the fleet management company policy (Redelbach and Friedrich, 2012) and after all the vehicle lifetime cost has been analyzed, the van selected is the one that has the lowest overall cost. An example could be the van powertrain efficiency and the costs associated to the propulsion energy and van acquisition and maintenance or the van resale value. These factors could have a great influence in the van cost per kilometer. That is the reason why a complete TCO study should include a multiple scenario analysis regarding multiple factors to reduce uncertainties, finding key user characteristics and compare costs of different van technologies, making it possible to determine when leading powertrain technologies become cost effective. However, TCO studies do not include costs that are difficult to measure, such as van reliability or range anxiety caused by an unexpected usage pattern that could have an important weight in the purchase decision.

The costs of a vehicle fleet are usually classified as direct and indirect costs. Indirect costs are those related, for example, to administrative personnel and facilities costs and are out of the scope of this study. Within the direct costs, we have considered those costs that are relevant from van ownership point of view and could be different for the different van technologies, therefore costs such as driver salaries and bank finance have not been considered.

Additionally, avoidable variable operating costs, for example tolls, fines or parking taxes have also not been taken into account. Nevertheless, it has been considered the decrease in the van value due to the operating conditions, such as the annual mileage, weight to be transported, environmental, traffic and road conditions, and company fleet maintenance policies. These factors will also have influence on variable operating costs because of wearing in van components and loss of powertrain efficiency. Figure 6 exposes the van fleet direct cost breakdown and the related cost parameters considered in this study.

Figure 6. Van fleet direct costs breakdown.

In this study they are also considered the costs related to the van energy infrastructure necessary to avoid dependence on public refueling/recharging points and downtimes in recharging events. In this case, it is also considered the operational and fixed costs. The infrastructure operation costs are based in energy consumption, annual maintenance cost and components replacement cost once the end of its useful life has been reached. Moreover, fixed costs are those related to purchase and power term costs. Figure 7 represents a scheme of the recharging/refueling infrastructure costs.

Figure 7. Recharging/refueling infrastructure costs.

Model formulation

The model exposed is relying on the minimization of the overall costs of the van fleet over a period. The optimization model extends the replacement model proposed by Figliozzi (Feng and Figliozzi, 2013) taking into account age replacement rules (Parthanadee et al., 2012) and economic analysis for the recharge infrastructure, including purchase and operational costs. In the case of fuel cell powered electric vans it is considered two different infrastructure cases for each one: (i) hydrogen purchased and delivered in 20 MPa high pressure cylinders, and (ii) on-site hydrogen generation using electrolyzers and electricity from the grid. Each type of hydrogen supply will be analyzed separately under several scenarios.

With the aim to facilitate the understanding of the model, Table 6 shows the nomenclature used in the model.

Table 6. Nomenclature used in the model.

Model set	Notation	Description
Indexes	k	The van type, where k = 1 for ICE-CNG, k = 2 for BEV, k = 3 for FC-EREV and k = 4 for FCEV
	i	The van age [year], where i = 0, 1, 2, ..., Nk
	r	Infrastructure type, where r = 1 for electric charger used in BEV, r = 2 for electric charger used in FC-EREV, r = 3 for hydrogen supply used in FC-EREV (purchased or generated), r = 4 for hydrogen supply used in FCEV (purchased or generated), and r = 5 for hydrogen dispenser that is a common part for infrastructures $r \in (3, 4)$
	m	Energy supply infrastructure age [year], where m = 0, 1, 2, ..., Nr
	j	The decision year in the time horizon considered [year], where j = 0, 1, 2, ..., T

Parameters	K_v	Types of vans considered	
	N_k	Ownership period of a van type “k” [year]	
	T	Horizon of time period [year]	
	fr_j	Discount rate in the current year “j”	
	VPC_{jk}	Van purchase cost of a type “k” van in year j [€/unit]	
	VRV_{ik}	Unit depreciation rate for an “i” years old “k” type van	
	FOC_{ijk}	Fixed operating costs of an “i” years old “k” type van in year “j” [€/year]	
	VEC_{ijk}	Energy costs for an “i” years old “k” type van in year “j” [€/km]	
	VMC_{ijk}	Maintenance costs for an “i” years old “k” type van in year “j” [€/km]	
	VRC_{ijk}	Repair costs for an “i” years old “k” type van in year “j” [€/km]	
	Dy_{ijk}	Annual utilization of an “i” years old “k” type van in year “j” [km/year]	
	N_y	Working days per year [day]	
	Dd_j	Daily fleet operator demand in year “j” [km/day]	
	$X0_{ik}$	Initial number of “i” years old “k” type van are in the fleet	
	R_i	Types of energy supply infrastructures considered	
	M_r	Ownership period of type “r” energy supply infrastructure [year]	
	IPC_{jr}	Type “r” energy supply infrastructure acquisition cost in year “j” [€/unit]	
	ISV_{mr}	Unit scrap rate of an “m” years old “r” type energy supply infrastructure	
	IMC_{mjr}	Infrastructure maintenance and repair costs for an “m” years old “r” type energy supply in year “j” [€/km]	
	IRC_{mjr}	Infrastructure repair costs for an “m” years old “r” type van energy supply in year “j” [€/year]	
	NSI_r	Number of vans that a type “r” energy supply infrastructure could serve	
	Decision variables	X_{ijk}	Number of in-use “i” years old “k” type van in year “j”
		S_{ijk}	Number of sold vans of type “k” with an age of “i” years at the end of the year “j”
P_{jk}		Number of purchased “k” type vans at the beginning of year “j”	
Y_{ijk}		Binary variable which has the 1 value when there are in-use “k” type vans at age “i”, or 0 value otherwise	
IX_{mjr}		Number of in-use “m” years old “r” type van energy supply infrastructures in year “j”	
IS_{mjr}		Number of scrapped energy supply infrastructures of type “r” with an age of “m” years when the year “j” ends	
IP_{jr}		Number of purchased “r” type energy supply infrastructure at the beginning of year “j” [unit]	

Thus, the optimization problem is based in a single objective function, Equation (1). The function is a sum of all related economic aspects of the van fleet for the operator point of view: cost and revenues. From the present time to the end of time horizon (T), in this study it has been considered 25 years.

$$\text{Minimize: } V_1 - V_2 + V_3 + I_1 - I_2 + I_3 \quad (1)$$

Where:

$$V_1 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K_v} VPC_{jk} \cdot P_{jk} \cdot f_{rj}$$

$$V_2 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{i=1}^{N_k} \sum_{k=1}^{K_v} VPC_{(j-i)k} \cdot VRV_{ik} \cdot S_{ijk} \cdot f_{rj}$$

$$V_3 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{i=0}^{N_k-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K_v} [(VEC_{ijk} + VMC_{ijk} + VRC_{ijk}) \cdot Dy_{ijk} + FOC_{ijk}] \cdot X_{ijk} \cdot f_{rj}$$

$$I_1 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{r=1}^{R_i} IPC_{jr} \cdot IP_{jr} \cdot f_{rj}$$

$$I_2 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M_r} \sum_{r=1}^{R_i} ISV_{mjr} \cdot IS_{mjr} \cdot f_{rj}$$

$$I_3 = \sum_{j=0}^{T-1} \sum_{m=0}^{M_r-1} \sum_{r=1}^{R_i} (IRC_{mjr} + IMC_{mjr}) \cdot IX_{mjr} \cdot f_{rj}$$

The optimization of the objective function is subjected to the constraints summarized in Equation (2) to Equation (29). The vans in the fleet have to meet the fleet operator distance demanded each year, Equation (2). At the beginning and in every year, the number of “k” type vans purchased should be equal to the new registrations of “k” type vans, Equation (3) and Equation (4). The initial number of k-type vans in the fleet must be equal to the sum of k-type vans in use plus sold vans at the end of the first period ($j = 0$), Equation (5). Equation (6) ensures the van number of vans balance from one year to the following. All the vans have to be sold at the end of last year considered in the analysis time horizon ($j = T$), Equation (7). When a van reaches the ownership period, it must be sold, Equation (8). A new van must be used before it could be sold and may not be sold up to a certain age, Equation (9) and Equation (10). The Equation (11) and Equation (12) are related to the replacement of older vehicles before newer ones. The replacement of older vehicles first, taking into account a non-decreasing pattern of operational costs, drives to a cost effective solution (Parthanadee et al., 2012). Equation (13) indicates that the van purchase costs cannot be higher than the annual budget that is sufficient enough to replace older vehicles with the more expensive van option. The number of electric charging points should be enough to recharge all the plug-in vans during the non-working period at the depot, Equation (14) and Equation (15). The hydrogen supply facilities should have enough capacity to refuel all the hydrogen powered vans at the depot every working day, Equation (16) and Equation (17). Equation (18) means that if there were any hydrogen vans, there must be at least one dispenser. There is an annual budget for the purchase of energy supply infrastructures, Equation (19). The infrastructure budget is high enough to purchase at least a complete hydrogen supply infrastructure. The number of “r” type infrastructures purchased has to be equal to the new “r” type infrastructures in use every year, Equation (20) and Equation (21). The equation (22) and Equation (23) ensure that the energy supply infrastructures should be operated over the complete

period of analysis. All the energy supply infrastructures should be scratched at the end of its lifetime, Equation (24), or at the end of the last year considered in the analysis time period ($j = T$), Equation (25). On the other hand, any infrastructure can be sold before it has reached its service life, Equation (26), or during its first year in operation, Equation (27). Finally, all the decision variables are integer-positive numbers, Equation (28), except the binary variable associated to replace older vans before rule, Equation (29).

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_k-1} \sum_{k=1}^{K_T} X_{ijk} \cdot U_{ijk} \geq N_y \cdot d_j \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (2)$$

$$P_{00k} + X_{00k} = X_{00k} \quad \forall k \quad (3)$$

$$P_{0jk} - X_{0jk} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall k \quad (4)$$

$$X_{i0k} + S_{i0k} = X_{i0k} \quad \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_k\}; \forall k \quad (5)$$

$$X_{(i-1)(j-1)k} = X_{ijk} + S_{ijk} \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall i \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_k\}; \forall k \quad (6)$$

$$X_{iT k} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N_k - 1\}; \forall k \quad (7)$$

$$X_{N_k/jk} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall k \quad (8)$$

$$S_{0jk} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\}; \forall k \quad (9)$$

$$S_{i0k} = 0 \quad \forall i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N_k\}; \forall k \quad (10)$$

$$X_{ijk} \leq R \cdot Y_{ijk} \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T-1\}; \forall i \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, N_k\}; \forall k \quad (11)$$

$$\sum_{n=0}^{i-1} S_{nj k} \leq R \cdot (1 - Y_{ijk}) \quad \forall j < T; \forall i < N_k; \forall k \quad (12)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{K_T} P_{1jk} \cdot VPC_{kj} \leq PVbudget_j \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (13)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_2-1} X_{ij2} \leq NSI_1 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_1-1} IX_{mj1} \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (14)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_2-1} X_{ij2} + \sum_{i=0}^{N_3-1} X_{ij3} \leq NSI_1 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_1-1} IX_{mj1} + NSI_2 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_2-1} IX_{mj2} \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (15)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_4-1} X_{ij4} \leq NSI_4 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_4-1} IX_{mj4} \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (16)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_3-1} X_{ij3} \leq NSI_3 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_3-1} IX_{mj3} + NSI_4 \cdot \sum_{m=0}^{M_4-1} IX_{mj4} \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (17)$$

$$\sum_{i=0}^{N_2-1} X_{ij3} + \sum_{i=0}^{N_4-1} X_{ij4} \leq NSI_5 \sum_{m=0}^{M_5-1} IX_{mj5} \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (18)$$

$$\sum_{r=1}^{R_i} IP_{1jk} \cdot IPC_{kj} \leq Plbudget_j \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\} \quad (19)$$

$$IP_{00r} + IX_{00r} = IX_{00r} \quad \forall r \quad (20)$$

$$IP_{0jr} - IX_{0jr} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall r \quad (21)$$

$$IS_{m0r} + IX_{m0r} = IX_{m0r} \quad \forall m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_r\}; \forall r \quad (22)$$

$$IX_{(m-1)(j-1)r} = IX_{mjv} + IS_{mjv} \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall m \in \{1, 2, \dots, M_r\}; \forall r \quad (23)$$

$$IX_{mTr} = 0 \quad \forall m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M_r - 1\}; \forall r \quad (24)$$

$$IX_{M_r jr} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{1, 2, \dots, T\}; \forall r \quad (25)$$

$$IS_{mjv} = 0 \quad \forall j \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, T-1\}; \forall m \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots, M_r - 1\}; \forall r \quad (26)$$

$$IS_{0Tr} = 0 \quad \forall r \quad (27)$$

$$X_{ijk}, S_{ijk}, P_{jk}, IX_{mjv}, IS_{mjv}, IP_{jr} \in \{0, 1, 2, \dots\} \quad (28)$$

$$Y_{ijk} \in \{0, 1\} \quad (29)$$

Model data.

The developed algorithm requires the use of a large amount of data, hence it has been necessary to prepare tables and mathematical expressions with purchase, operation, maintenance and disposal costs for the vehicle and the energy supply infrastructure depending on van type and age in every time period. Furthermore a subsequent sensitivity analysis (Morrison et al., 2018) will be performed to consider the effects of possible variations of these data in long time horizons.

In this study it is compared the future investments in different van technologies over a period of time therefore it must be considered the purchasing power of money and set it to the present time. To this end it is incorporated in the expression of total cost of ownership the discount factor rate as is showed in Equation (30).

$$TDCO = \sum_{j=0}^T CT_j \cdot (1+r)^j \cdot f_{rj} \quad (30)$$

Where:

CT_j is the annual total costs [€/year]

T is the time horizon considered [year]

r is the inflation rate. Several inflation rates are used depending on the concept considered according to

Table 7.

f_j is the discount factor defined as:

$$f_j = \frac{1}{(1+r_d)^j}$$

r_d is the discount rate considered for the time horizon.

The discount rate considered in the study is 2% which is consistent with the average yield of the Spanish Treasury in 2020 (Tesoro Público, 2022). Conversely, the inflation rate considered is different for each concept (vehicles, capital goods, maintenance and repair service and spare parts) and it is applied in each cost individually. The value used in the model is an average of the last ten years values from INE (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2021) statistics. These values are summarized in Table 7.

Table 7. Inflation rate average for different concepts (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2021).

Concept	Value [%]	Note
General index (r_{GEN})	1,3	
New vehicles (r_{VAN})	2,0	
Used vehicles (r_{2HND})	0,0	(1)
Maintenance & repair services ($r_{M\&R}$)	1,8	
Spare parts (r_{SP})	0,6	
Vehicle insurances (r_{IN})	1,1	
Capital goods (r_{CG})	1,2	

Table notes: (1) Second-hand vehicle market has seen a large variation in prices over the last few years, going from positive to negative inflation rates. For this reason, the authors have decided to use a zero value for the inflation rate.

Retail price and depreciation costs are determinant for the purchase decision. In this research the authors has assumed that the vans are purchased at the beginning of each year and sold at the end. The van purchase cost considered are the retail price in Spain at present time for the market available vans, this is the case of the CNG and battery electric powered vans. On the other hand, the retail price for the hydrogen powered vans is estimated using the equivalent battery electric van retail price modified with the specific component costs, such as modified battery capacity and on-board charger, the hydrogen tank and the fuel cell and its peripheral components as is expressed in Equation (31). Their average prices are extracted from literature and can be consulted in Table 8 (Electrification Coalition, 2010; Ramsden, 2013; Parks et al., 2014; Kleiner and Friedrich, 2017b; Trost et al., 2017; Giordano et al., 2018; James et al., 2018; Thompson et al., 2018; Ruf, Yvonne et al., 2020; Handwerker et al., 2021), and the van purchase cost considered in Table 9.

$$VPC = VPC_{BEV} - (B_{CP} - B_{CP-P}) \cdot B_C + FC_C \cdot FC_{FW} + T_C \cdot T_{CP} \quad (31)$$

Where:

VPC is the van purchase cost [€]

VPC_{BEV} is the purchase cost of the equivalent battery electric van [€]

B_C is the battery cost [€/kWh]

B_{CP-F} is the battery nameplate capacity of fuel cell powered van [kWh]

B_{CP} is the battery nameplate capacity of battery electric powered van [kWh]

FC_C is the fuel cell and peripheral components cost [€/kW]

FC_{PW} is the fuel cell power [kW]

T_C is the hydrogen tank cost [€/kg H2]

T_{CP} is the hydrogen tank capacity [kg H2]

Table 8. Prices of fuel cell powertrain components.

Component	Unit	Cost
Vehicle battery	(€/kWh)	240
FC stack and peripheral components	(€/kW)	355
H2 Type IV H2 storage tank	(€/kg)	650

Table 9. Van purchase cost.

Van type	Purchase cost [€]
ICE-CNG	37.385
BEV	51.520
FC-EREV	51.865
FCEV	71.450

In Equation (32) is calculated the resale value (VRV) using the purchase price (VPC) and the depreciation rate (VDR) estimated in the Equation (33). This equation is based on the relationship developed by Kleiner (Kleiner and Friedrich, 2017c) for N1 vehicle category that uses experimental coefficients and the average annual mileage (D_y) in kilometers.

$$VRV = (1 - VDR) \cdot VPC \tag{32}$$

$$VDR = 1 - \left(a \cdot 10^{\left(b \frac{D_y}{1000} \right)} \right), \text{ with constants: } a = 8,79E-01; b = -8,00E-03 \tag{33}$$

Insurance fees used are based on retail price and expected mileage of the vehicle (Van Bokhorst et al., 2017). The insurance costs considered are an average of prices consulted on the Internet with the main insurance companies in the country.

In Spain is applied a 75% reduction in the circulation taxes for zero-emission vehicles. Technical inspection fee and freight transport taxes are equal for all the vehicle configurations analyzed and they are not considered. The insurances fees and circulation taxes for the different vans are showed in Table 10. The operation fixed costs (OFC) is calculated according to Equation (34) (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2021).

$$FOC_{ijk} = (TX + IN)_{ik} \cdot (1 + r_{GEN})^j \quad (34)$$

Where:

TX is the tax fee [€/year] (Table 10)

IN is the insurance price [€/year]

r_{GEN} is the inflation rate general index (Table 7)

Table 10. Insurance fees and circulation taxes for different van types.

Van type	Cost	Value [€/year]
ICE-CNG	Taxes	149
	Insurance	2.243
BEV	Taxes	37
	Insurance	3.091
FC-EREV	Taxes	37
	Insurance	2.749
FCEV	Taxes	37
	Insurance	4.287

The energy costs per kilometer are calculated as a function of van energy consumption and energy prices applying Equation (35).

$$VEC_{ijk} = EC_{jk} \cdot E_{ik} \quad (35)$$

Where:

EC_{jk} is the energy price for the van propulsion [€/kWh] or [€/kg]

E_{ik} is the van energy consumption [kWh/km] or [kg/km]

For plug-in electric vans, energy consumption includes the charging efficiency. It has been considered a slow charging mode average efficiency of 87% (Trentadue et al., 2018; Ligen et al., 2018).

Energy costs per kilometer of a FC-EREV are dependent on the utility factor (UF) calculated as a function of daily mileage (D_d) and the electricity range, as it is expressed in Equation (36). As a reference, a BEV should have a value for UF equal to the unit while in the case of FCEVs it should be zero. FC-EREVs firstly operate in charge depleting mode (CD) until the battery state of charge (SoC) achieves a fixed value and then battery energy management switch to charge sustaining mode (CS). Authors have considered that energy consumption in CD mode comes from the electricity stored in the battery, but in the case of CS mode, energy is obtained from hydrogen stored in the tank. On the other hand, this hydrogen may come from an external supplier or on-site generated using water electrolysis. In the first option, it is only considered the compressor, cooling system and other auxiliary components consumption, but in the latter case, it is also considered the consumption of the electrolyzer per kilogram of hydrogen produced. All the electricity consumed by the vans comes from the grid.

$$UF = \frac{D_d}{R_e} \quad (36)$$

Where:

D_d is the daily utilization [km]

R_e is the useful electricity range [km]

Then, the electricity consumption per kilometer in a FC-EREV comes from the recharging of the battery and from hydrogen supply. Equation (37) allows the calculation of grid electricity consumption if the hydrogen is purchased or if it is generated on-site using an electrolyzer.

$$E_i = \frac{C_e}{\eta_{CH}} + \rho_{H2} \cdot C_{H2} \cdot (1 - UF) \quad (37)$$

Where:

η_{CH} is the battery charging efficiency

C_e is the van electricity consumption [kWh/km]

ρ_{H2} is the hydrogen supply components efficiency [kWh/kg] (Table 5)

C_{H2} is the van hydrogen consumption [kg/km]

For large periods of time, it is difficult to estimate the annual energy prices evolution, in particular for hydrogen. The energy prices used in this study are explained in Appendix B.

The maintenance cost (VMC) calculation is based on the age and annual mileage (Dy) (Electrification Coalition, 2010) according to the Equation (38). In this Equation the maintenance cost for CNG vans is used as a reference for the calculation of the BEV, FC-EREV and FCEV maintenance costs applying different c_k factors. In this way, for BEV van it is considered a 50% reduction in the maintenance cost ($c_2 = 0,5$) with respect to the CNG van due to less powertrain complex construction (Electrification Coalition, 2010; Feng and Figliozzi, 2013; Taefi, 2016; Giordano et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2018). However, hydrogen fuel cell powertrains are composed by more components than a BEV thus the maintenance cost reduction with respect to the CNG van is 40% for FC-EREV vans ($c_3 = 0,6$) and 30% for FCEV vans ($c_4 = 0,7$) (Ramsden, 2013; Kleiner and Friedrich, 2017c; Trost et al., 2017; Ruf et al., 2020).

$$VMC_{ijk} = \left(\frac{Dy}{20.000} \right) \cdot d \cdot c_k \cdot (\alpha \cdot i + b) \cdot (1 + r_{M\&R})^j, \quad (38)$$

Where:

$r_{M\&R}$ is the maintenance and repair inflation rate

a, b, d are constants with the following values:

$$d = 0,04; \alpha = 0,4752; b = 0,6467$$

c_k are factors with different values depending on the van type

(CNG, $k = 1$; BEV, $k = 2$; FC-EREV, $k = 3$; FCEV, $k = 4$)

$$c_1 = 1; c_2 = 0,5; c_3 = 0,6; c_4 = 0,7$$

The van repair cost (VRC) calculation is based on the annual mileage (Dy) and powertrain components lifetime, mainly hydrogen fuel cell stack and the battery, according to Equation (39). In the spare parts estimation

costs showed in Table 11 (Thompson et al., 2018; Giordano et al., 2018; James et al., 2018; Handwerker et al., 2021) are summarized average values available in the literature.

$$VRC_{ijk} = (\delta B_{ik} \cdot RB_c + \delta FC_{ik} \cdot RFC_c) \cdot (1 + r_{M\&R})^j \quad (39)$$

Where:

$r_{M\&R}$ is the maintenance and repair inflation rate

δB_{ik} is a binary variable, that takes value one when the battery has to be replaced.

$$\delta B_i = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{i \cdot D_y}{Blf_k} \right) \geq 1$$

Blf_k is the lifetime of the battery for each technology [km]

δFC_{jk} is a binary variable, , that takes value one when the fuel cell stack has to be replaced.

$$\delta FC_{jk} = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{j \cdot D_y}{FClf_k} \right) \geq 1$$

$FClf_k$ is the lifetime of the fuel cell stack for each technology [km]

RB_c is the cost of van battery replacement [€]

RFC_c is the cost of van PEM fuel cell stack replacement [€]

Table 11. Spare parts cost.

Component	Value [€/kWh]
Battery replacement	100
Fuel cell stack replacement	180

The recharging infrastructure consists on a Mode 3 and a Mode 2 charger for the BEV and the FC-EREV vans respectively. It is considered that the vans will be recharged at the depot at the end of the business day. Therefore the charger quantity of each type will depend on the number of vans that compose the fleet, the available time for charging, the energy consumed in the daily delivery and the power capacity of the on board charger due to the installed chargers at the depot have plenty of power. Hence, as the number of vans in the fleet is known then the number of chargers could be calculated using the number of vans per electric charger (NV_e) determined with Equation (40), and it is possible to estimate the cost for the electric charging infrastructure by multiplying the number of chargers by their unit cost

$$NV_e = \frac{t_{dCH}}{t_{CH}} \quad (40)$$

Where:

t_{dCH} is the available daily time to charge [hours], 10 hours are considered in this study

t_{CH} is the time needed to recharge the battery [hours], defined as:

$$t_{CH} = \frac{B_e}{OBC_{pw}} \cdot UF, \text{ with:}$$

B_e is the battery useful energy [kWh]

OBC_{pw} is the van on board charger power [kW]

UF is the utility factor defined in Equation (36)

The total purchase cost of infrastructure (IPC) expressed in Equation (41) is defined as the sum of the individual components cost and the installation expenses, these costs are function of the unit costs showed in the Table 12 (Electrification Coalition, 2010; DOE, 2014; Parks et al., 2014; Elgowainy et al., 2017; Reddi et al., 2017; Tractebel et al., 2017; (Grouset and Ridart, 2018); Mayyas and Mann, 2019; Ulleberg and Hancke, 2020; Schücking and Jochem, 2021).

$$IPC_r = \left(1 + \frac{r_{IN}}{100}\right) \cdot \sum INC_{comp} \quad (41)$$

Where:

r_{IN} installation cost rate

INC_{comp} infrastructure cost of several components (EV charger, electrolyzer, compressor, cooling system, buffer tank and dispenser)

Table 12. Infrastructure components estimated costs.

Component	Unit	Value	Note
H2 dispenser (single hose)	(€/ud)	65.000	
Cooling system	(€)	48.160	
H2 buffer tanks 925bar	(€/kg day)	840	
H2 infrastructure M&R cost rate	(%)	4,0	(1)
H2 infrastructure installation cost rate	(%)	20	(2)
E charger (Mode 3)	(€/ud)	13.300	(3)
E charger (Mode 2)	(€/ud)	3.500	(3)

Table notes: (1) Typically in industrial environment the infrastructure maintenance cost is estimated in the range of 2 to 4% of the purchase and installation cost; (2) Construction labor cost percentage commonly accepted is in the range from 10 to 30% of total costs; (3) The price includes the installation costs.

The electrolyzer, compressor, high pressure buffer tanks and cooling system costs are based on the hydrogen flow rate production capacity per hour (Q_{H_2}) needed for the fleet calculated in Equation (43) that will depend on daily hydrogen fleet consumption (CF_{dH_2}) and the installation utilization rate per day (IN_{UR}) given that hydrogen is stored in high pressure tanks ready to be pumped to the vehicle. It is considered a minimum hydrogen consumption in FC-EREV vans of 0,01 kg per day even if the electric range of the van is capable of making the entire trip in electric mode.

The electrolyzer cost, see Equation (42), is function of the installed electric power according to the observed literature (Tractebel et al., 2017; Caponi et al., 2021; Handwerker et al., 2021). In this Equation, it has been taken into account the electrolyzer idle time using an installation utilization rate of 0,7 (IN_{UR}).

$$INC_{H2_{EL}} = 12.763 \cdot (E_{EL} - Q_{H2})^{-0.226} \quad (42)$$

where:

E_{EL} electrolyzer installed electric power [kW/Nm³] (Table 5)

Q_{H2} hydrogen flow rate production capacity [kg/h] calculated according to Equation (43)

$$Q_{H2} = \frac{CF_{dH2}}{24 \cdot IN_{UR}} \quad (43)$$

Where:

IN_{UR} is the installation utilization rate

CF_{dH2} is the daily hydrogen fleet consumption [kg/day], see Equation (44)

$$CF_{dH2} = N_{dR} \cdot T_{H2} \quad (44)$$

Where:

T_{H2} is the van hydrogen tank capacity [kg]

N_{dR} is the number of refuelings per day defined in Equation (45)

$$N_{dR} = \frac{N_{H2van}}{t_{dH2}} \quad (45)$$

Where:

N_{H2van} is the number of hydrogen vans in the fleet

t_{dH2} is the number of days between refuelings determined with Equation (46)

$$t_{dH2} = \frac{T_{H2}}{C_{dH2}}, \quad (46)$$

Where:

C_{dH2} is the van hydrogen daily consumption [kg/day] defined as:

$C_{dH2} = D_d \cdot C_{H2} \cdot (1 - UF)$, where C_{H2} represents the hydrogen consumption [kg/km] and D_d is the daily distance travelled [km].

The high pressure buffer tanks cost is function of the daily hydrogen fleet consumption and the respective unit cost as it is expressed in Equation (47).

$$INC_{H2_{TK}} = C_{TK} \cdot CF_{dH2} \quad (47)$$

Where:

C_{TK} hydrogen high pressure buffer tank unit cost [€/kg H₂ day] (Table 12)

CF_{H_2} daily hydrogen fleet consumption [kg/day] according to Equation (44)

Hydrogen compressor cost, see Equation (48), is function of the hydrogen flow rate production capacity needed in compliance with literature (Elgowainy et al., 2017; Grouset and Ridart, 2018; Mayyas and Mann, 2019).

$$INC_{H_2,CMP} = 57.953 \cdot (Q_{H_2})^{-0.766} \quad (48)$$

Where:

Q_{H_2} hydrogen flow rate production capacity [kg/h] according to Equation (43)

Due to the hydrogen dispenser flow rate considered is 2 kg/min, in the worst scenario with a van daily consumption of 2 kg it would be possible to refuel up to 360 vans per day. Therefore, we can consider that it is only needed one dispenser with a single hose.

Finally, the installation cost is formulated as a rate of the component costs and includes the setting up labor and other installation component's cost, such as valves, piping, filters, etc.

Both types of infrastructure need electric power. In Spain there is a fixed tax named power term that the company pays for the amount of electric power available, which determines the number of electric devices that can be connected at the same time. This tax must be satisfied even if no electricity is consumed. According to regulated energy prices report of the Spanish institution IDAE (Instituto para la Diversificación y el Ahorro de Energía, 2022), the power term tax for transport and distribution for installed power over 15 kW is 16,67 €/kW per year.

The maintenance cost of the infrastructure (IMC) is calculated using Equation (49) and it is based in a rate of the purchase and installation cost as it is showed in Table 12 and updated annually with the maintenance and repairing inflation rate.

$$IMC_{tj} = (IPC_t \cdot r_{IN_M\&R}) \cdot (1 + r_{GEN})^j \quad (49)$$

Where:

IPC_t is the infrastructure purchase and installation cost [€]

$r_{IN_M\&R}$ is the infrastructure maintenance and repairing cost rate (Table 12)

r_{GEN} general inflation rate index (Table 7)

For the repairing costs it has been considered the lifetime of electric charger, electrolyzer, high pressure compressor, cooling system and hydrogen dispenser. The repairing cost (IRC) calculation in Equation (50) is based on the average lifetime of the components shown in Table 5. For the spare parts costs in Table 13 it has been considered average future values from the literature (DOE, 2014; Parks et al., 2014; Tractebel et al., 2017; Grouset and Ridart, 2018; Mayyas and Mann, 2019; Schücking and Jochem, 2021).

$$IRC_{ijr} = (\delta CH_{ir} \cdot RCH_C + \delta EL_{ir} \cdot REL_C + \delta CMP_{ir} \cdot RCMP_C + \delta DSP_{ir} \cdot RDSP_C) \cdot (1 + r_{M\&R})^j \quad (50)$$

Where:

$r_{M\&R}$ is the maintenance and repairing inflation rate (Table 7)

δCH_{ir} , is a binary variable that takes the value one when it is necessary to replace the electric charger.

$$\delta CH_{it} = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{i}{CHlf_t} \right) \geq 1$$

$CHlf_t$ is the lifetime of the electric charger for each technology [years]

δEL_{it} is a binary variable that takes the value one when it is necessary to replace the electrolyzer fuel cell stack.

$$\delta EL_{it} = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{i}{ELlf_t} \right) \geq 1$$

$ELlf_t$ is the lifetime of the electrolyzer fuel cell stack for each technology [years]

δCMP_{it} is a binary variable that takes the value one when it is necessary to replace the compressor.

$$\delta CMP_{it} = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{i}{CMPlf_t} \right) \geq 1$$

$CMPlf_t$ is the lifetime of the compressor [years]

δDSP_{it} is a binary variable that takes the value one when it is necessary to replace the hydrogen dispenser and cooling system.

$$\delta DSP_{it} = 1 \text{ if } \left(\frac{i}{DSPlf_t} \right) \geq 1$$

$DSPlf_t$ is the lifetime of the hydrogen dispenser [years]

RCH_c is the cost of a new charger [€]

REL_c is the spare fuel cell stack cost [€]

$RCMP_c$ is the cost of a compressor refurbishment [€]

$RDSP_c$ is the cost of the hydrogen dispenser and cooling system refurbishment [€]

Table 13. Spare parts estimated cost for infrastructure components.

Component	Unit	Value
Spare fuel cell stack	(€/kW)	1000
H ₂ buffer tanks 925bar	(€/kg day)	840
H ₂ dispenser (single hose) and cooling system refurbishment	(€/each)	45.000
H ₂ compressor refurbishment	(€/kg day)	1.000

Finally, at the end of study time horizon all the infrastructure components will be scrapped considering a residual value of 5% of purchase price.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The developed linear programming optimizer algorithm has been performed over a set of proposed scenarios. The algorithm output for each scenario is the cost per kilometer, the van CAPEX and OPEX, the infrastructure CAPEX and OPEX, cost saving with respect to business as usual van fleet case (i.e. all CNG type vans), and the average of van powertrain types over the time considered in the study. Under the CAPEX term is collected the purchase cost and the revenues from sale or scratch a company asset, this is a van or an infrastructure. Moreover, the OPEX term is the sum of all the operational costs, fixed and variable ones. Furthermore, the average powertrain types provides information about the most suitable van type option and the degree of replacement of the initial van powertrain technology, in this case CNG vans, with an alternative option.

The behavior of each scenario depends on three definition variables and the hydrogen source pathway that has been considered. The scenario definition variables are chosen from among the variables of the model those related to fleet operator's requirements, such as, average annual distance travelled, van ownership period and the size of the van fleet. The remaining variables of the model, such as discount and inflation rate, energy costs, power term price, van purchase price and maintenance cost, are labeled as economic variables. On the other side, it has been considered two hydrogen source pathways, purchased and on-site production. The combination of definition variables and hydrogen source pathways generate 14 scenarios presented in Table 14.

This section is organized in four parts: (i) scenario modelling, (ii) explanation of the sensitive and breakeven analysis conducted (iii) results and analysis regarding the purchased hydrogen case, (iv) results and analysis regarding generated hydrogen case, and finally (v) a summary of findings.

Scenario modelling

As it has been explained before the scenario characteristics depend on three definition variables and two hydrogen source pathways. The scenario definition variables are: average annual distance travelled, van ownership period and the size of the van fleet. The values selected for the annual utilization and ownership period come from the van market characteristics in Spain. On the other hand, the van fleet size values reflect different company categories of logistic services, from small to large scale. In Table 14 is summarized the values used for the definition variables in the different scenarios. In all the scenarios the initial van fleet is composed entirely by CNG powered vans.

Table 14. Scenario variables.

Variable	Unit	Scenarios						
		Baseline	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6
H2 source		Purchased (P) or Generated (G)						
Annual distance	km	30.000	20.000	40.000	30.000	30.000	30.000	30.000
Ownership period	years	8	8	8	5	10	8	8
Van fleet	units	200	200	200	200	200	80	320

The baseline scenario reflects a usual Spanish van fleet behavior with average van mileage over 20.000 km per year and ownership period around eight years and it is supposed 200 vehicles in the fleet. The set of economic variables used corresponds to the business as usual values of these variables as it is explained in the model data section. Afterwards, a sensitive and breakeven analysis will be conducted in some selected scenarios in order to take into account the influence of these economic variables on fleet cost and van type selection. The scenarios are selected based on within the most commonly powertrain used is FC-EREV or FCEV.

Sensitive and breakeven analysis methodology

The objective of the sensitive analysis is to determine the effect of the model variables on the fleet per kilometer cost. However, the breakeven analysis purpose is to determine the value of a model variable which becomes a van type the best option compared to the others.

The sensitive analysis performed is based on an elasticity test in order to reflect the influence of each model variable over the fleet per kilometer cost. The formulation used is the arc elasticity, see Equation (51).

$$E(C_k, X_{ik}) = \frac{\frac{\Delta C_k / C_k}{\Delta X_{ik} / X_{ik}}}{\frac{\Delta X_{ik} / X_{ik}}{\Delta X_{ik} / X_{ik}}} \quad (51)$$

Where:

C_k is per kilometer cost in “k” scenario

X_{ik} represents the variable “i” in “k” scenario

The sensitive analysis is carried out in two steps. The first step consists in an elasticity test on the scenario definition variables, comparing scenarios in which only one of the variables changes, in order to detect the most relevant definition variables in the cost per kilometer. The second step is to perform a new optimization run over the scenarios that contains the most relevant definition variables. In these scenarios, it will be changed the economic variables one by one. In the case of the discount rate, the new value selected is according to the maximum long term interest rate in Spain in the last 20 years (European Central Bank, 2022). Furthermore, the inflation rate variation is applied to all the inflation rates considered in the study, see Table 7, and the chosen value is in accordance with the general inflation rate variation over the last ten years (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2021). Afterwards, over these optimization results will be performed a new elasticity test.

On the other hand, there are some economic variables with a certain degree of uncertainty in its value over time that could affect to the van type selected. Therefore it has been performed a breakeven analysis to determine what specific values of these variables give rise to the choice of one van option or the other. The breakeven value for a specific economic variable is defined as the value which causes that the van average percentage over time under analysis become over 80% with a different van type compared to the base scenario of the economic variable analyzed. With this aim, the economic variables will be changed one by one in each optimization run until the van type average percentage change constraint is fulfilled.

Purchased hydrogen case

The elasticity analysis conducted over scenario definition variables (Table 15) reveals that the annual distance travelled and to a lesser extent the ownership period has a strong influence over the fleet per kilometer

costs, but the fleet size does not significantly affect. These trends can be observed in the CAPEX and OPEX values for the different scenarios reflected in Figure 8 where the OPEX costs are higher than CAPEX in all the scenarios, except for S3P scenario with a short ownership period, and does not show noticeable changes in per kilometer cost with the van fleet size.

Table 15. Cost elasticity to definition variables in purchased hydrogen case.

Variable	Elasticity values (E)						
	Baseline	S1P	S2P	S3P	S4P	S5P	S6P
Annual distance	-	-0,39	-0,27	-	-	-	-
Ownership period	-	-	-	-0,15	-0,04	-	-
Van fleet size	-	-	-	-	-	-0,01	-0,01

Figure 8. Results for purchased hydrogen case: total CAPEX, OPEX and cost per kilometer.

On the other hand, the CAPEX and OPEX cost breakdown for each scenario is displayed in Figure 9. In this graph can be observed:

- The van costs are much more relevant than the infrastructure costs in all the scenarios analyzed.
- The cost distribution between vehicle and infrastructure is approximately the same except for small fleets (scenario S5P), where the infrastructure cost is around 48% higher compared to the average of the other scenarios.

Figure 9. Results for purchased hydrogen case: CAPEX and OPEX breakdown.

In Table 16 it can be observed that the preferred van powertrain option is the FC-EREV in all the scenarios with a maximum substitution rate over 90% in S2P scenario. The advantage of FC-EREV is due to the lowest energy consumption per kilometer, an average hydrogen price around 4,2 €/kg and a similar purchase cost with BEV option, despite the higher maintenance and repair costs. Other results that can be derived from Table 16 are:

- The van type distribution in each scenario depends mainly on the annual distance travelled, with high annual kilometers utilization the percentage of new van types is higher.
- The average time with alternative vans is also higher in the scenarios with higher distances. The value goes from 68% in the 20.000 km scenario (S1P) to 80% in the 40.000 km scenario (S2P). This means that the substitution of conventional vans starts sooner.
- Moreover, the ownership period and the van fleet size do not affect substantially with around 86% of substitution rate.

Table 16. Van type distribution in each scenario for purchased hydrogen case.

Van type	Unit	Scenario results						
		Baseline	S1P	S2P	S3P	S4P	S5P	S6P
CNG ⁽¹⁾	(%)	14,0	15,9	9,9	14,0	13,7	14,6	13,9
BEV ⁽¹⁾	(%)	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
FC-EREV ⁽¹⁾	(%)	86,0	84,1	90,1	86,0	86,3	85,4	86,1
FCEV ⁽¹⁾	(%)	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Percentage of time where alternative vans are greater than 90%	(%)	76,0	68,0	80,0	76,0	76,0	76,0	76,0

Table captions: (1) Percentage of vans in average of a given van type over the time under analysis

Additionally, Figure 10 shows that cost savings with respect to business as usual van fleet scenario, where all the vehicles have a CNG powertrain. In this graph it can be observed that the cost savings grows with the annual kilometers travelled, the ownership period and to a lesser extent with the van fleet size.

Figure 10. Results for purchased hydrogen case: cost savings compared to BAU scenario.

The annual kilometer and the ownership period scenarios have the most relevance in the cost per kilometer and therefore these scenarios will be used for the subsequent sensitive and breakeven analysis.

Sensitive analysis.

The results of the sensitive analysis for purchased hydrogen case in the selected scenarios are exposed in Table 17. Discount and inflation rate have the largest elasticity absolute value, followed, in order of importance, by the fuel cell powertrain maintenance and the FC powered van purchase cost, and finally, electricity and gas price. In contrast, hydrogen price only has importance in case of very high annual distance travelled and the power term has no significance. As it can be observed, a slightly increment in the FC-EREV van purchase price (10%) causes a change in the preferred van type, becoming BEV van the best option. A similar behavior appears with a 10%

increment in the fuel cell maintenance price. However, a reduction in electricity or gas price does not affect to the preferred van option, as well as the discount or inflation rate variation, and the FC-EREV continues to be the selected van type. This trend, together with the insensitivity to hydrogen price, could be explained due to the FC-EREV electricity range, that is large enough to fulfill most of the distance required by the fleet operator, and then, the hydrogen consumption is lower.

Table 17. Cost elasticity to economic variables in purchased hydrogen case.

	Unit	Variable value		Elasticity values (E)									
				Baseline		S1P		S2P		S3P		S4P	
		Ref.	New	E ⁽¹⁾	PVO ⁽²⁾	E	PVO	E	PVO	E	PVO	E	PVO
Discount rate	(%)	2,5	6	-0,38	FCEREV	-0,38	FCEREV	-0,38	FCEREV	-0,39	FCEREV	-0,38	FCEREV
Inflation rate	(weight factor) ⁽⁵⁾	1	2,5	0,31	FCEREV	0,33	FCEREV	0,30	FCEREV	0,35	FCEREV	0,30	FCEREV
Average electricity price ⁽³⁾	(€/kWh)	0,168	0,151	0,06	FCEREV	0,08	FCEREV	0,05	FCEREV	0,05	FCEREV	0,06	FCEREV
Average hydrogen price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	4,195	4,614	0,01	FCEREV	-0,02	FCEREV	0,05	FCEREV	0,01	FCEREV	0,01	FCEREV
Average CNG price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	2,695	2,425	0,06	FCEREV	0,04	FCEREV	0,05	FCEREV	0,01	FCEREV	0,06	FCEREV
FC van price ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,1	0,08	BEV	0,04	BEV	0,12	BEV	0,18	BEV	0,05	BEV
Power term price	(€/Kw year)	16,67	15,00	0,00	FCEREV	-0,02	FCEREV	0,00	FCEREV	0,00	FCEREV	0,00	FCEREV
FC van maintenance cost ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,1	0,11	BEV	0,13	FCEREV	0,15	BEV	0,11	FCEREV	0,06	BEV

Table captions: (1) E: elasticity value, (2) PVO: preferred van option, (3) Energy price is calculated as an average over the years considered in the study, (4) Under the denomination FC powered van are encompassed FCEV and FC-EREV types, (5) The reference variable values are multiplied by 1,1 factor.

Breakeven analysis.

The results of the breakeven analysis are exposed in Table 18. As it was explained in the sensitive and breakeven analysis methodology section, the breakeven value for a specific economic variable causes that more than 80% of the van fleet in the time under analysis are composed with a different van type compared to the base scenario of the economic variable analyzed. For example, an average electricity price of 0,09 €/kWh instead of 0,168 €/kWh in the baseline scenario causes the selected van to be the BEV type instead of the FC-EREV type. The results derived from Table 18 indicate that:

- With an average electricity price under 0,09 €/kWh in scenarios with an yearly distance demand over 30.000 km and ownership period over 8 years the best option is a BEV van. Nevertheless if the annual

distance is less than 20.000 km or ownership period is less than five years FC-EREV van type remains as the option of choice.

- If the yearly distance demand is over 30.000 km and the ownership period is over 8 years, if the average hydrogen price grows over 6,5 €/kg the chosen van option will be the BEV type. Nevertheless with short ownership periods, below 5 years, or moderate annual distances, under 30.000 km the average hydrogen price should be over 8,81 €/kg or 13,21 €/kg respectively.
- It is necessary to reduce the average CNG price under 1,68 €/kg to cause a change to CNG van option in the best case scenario for this powertrain technology (S1P). When the ownership period grows over 10 years, or annual mileage is high, over 40.000 km, the average CNG price must be excessively low, which an unrealistic value.
- A slight increase in the selling price of the FC-EREV van leads to a change in the type of van chosen. This behavior is manifested in annual distances less than 30.000 km and ownership periods over 8 years, where the admissible increase in the FC-EREV retail price is less than 2%. Nevertheless, if the annual distance is over 40.000 km and the ownership periods are less than eight years it is possible to achieve selling price increases of more than 3%. This is due to the different life span of the battery and fuel cell stack for each powertrain technology.
- Long ownership periods, over 8 years, and high annual distances, over 30.000 km, make that the breakeven point for fuel cell maintenance goes to lower values. In these cases, the allowable increment in maintenance costs for fuel cell powered vans are less than 7% to become competitive compared to BEV vans. Nevertheless, if the ownership period or annual distances are short, below 5 years and 20.000 km respectively, the breakeven point for fuel cell maintenance costs for FC-EREV vans can be up to 11% and 18% respectively more expensive to remain as the best option. The explanation to this trend is, as in the selling price, the different life span of the battery and fuel cell stack for each powertrain technology

Table 18. Breakeven analysis results in purchased hydrogen case.

	Unit	Variable base value	Scenario results									
			Baseline		S1P		S2P		S3P		S4P	
			BP ⁽¹⁾	PVO ⁽²⁾	BP	PVO	BP	PVO	BP	PVO	BP	PVO
Average electricity price ⁽³⁾	(€/kWh)	0,168	0,09	BEV	NBP ⁽⁵⁾	FCEREV	0,09	BEV	NBP	FCEREV	0,11	BEV
Average hydrogen price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	4,195	8,81	BEV	NBP	FCEREV	6,50	BEV	13,21	BEV	6,50	BEV
Average CNG price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	2,695	1,00	CNG	1,68	CNG	0,24	CNG	1,40	CNG	0,40	CNG
FC van price ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor) ⁽⁵⁾	1	1,02	BEV	1,02	BEV	1,04	BEV	1,03	BEV	1,01	BEV
FC van maintenance cost ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,07	BEV	1,11	BEV	1,07	BEV	1,18	BEV	1,03	BEV

Table captions: (1) BP: breaking point value of the variable analyzed, (2) PVO: preferred van option, (3) Energy price is calculated as an average over the years considered in the study, (4) Under the denomination FC powered van are encompassed FCEV and FC-EREV types, (5) NBP, means no break point value available because the variable value is unrealistic (too high or too low), (5) The reference variable values are multiplied by 1,1 factor.

Generated hydrogen case

If we analyze the powertrain option rate distribution in this case (see Table 19), the BEV van option is the preferred van type in all the cases except for the scenario S1G with low annual mileages (20.000 km). In this scenario case, FC-EREV van option is preferred based on its lower electricity consumption per kilometer and the similar purchase price with the BEV van. Because, daily distances can be travelled in electric mode the annual hydrogen consumption is very low and the infrastructure requirements can be fulfilled with a very small scale hydrogen installation. In this sense, the elasticity analysis conducted reflects the BEV van type behavior in the different scenarios but not the influence of the hydrogen infrastructure.

Table 19. Van type distribution in each scenario for generated hydrogen case.

Van type	Unit	Scenario results						
		Baseline	S1G	S2G	S3G	S4G	S5G	S6G
CNG	(%)	14,1	15,8	10,2	11,5	14,6	14,7	14,0
BEV	(%)	85,9	0,0	89,8	88,5	85,4	85,4	86,0
FCEREV	(%)	0,0	84,2	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
FCEV	(%)	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0
Percentage of time where alternative vans are greater than 90%	(%)	76,0	68,0	80,0	80,0	72,0	76,0	76,0

Table captions: (1) Percentage of vans in average of a given type over time under analysis

The elasticity results in Table 20 shows the same trends as the FC-EREV van type predominant scenarios in the hydrogen purchase case, the annual distance and the ownership period are the most significant variables.

Table 20. Cost elasticity to definition variables in generated hydrogen case.

Model parameter	Scenario results						
	Baseline	S1G	S2G	S3G	S4G	S5G	S6G
Annual distance	-	-0,37	-0,25	-	-	-	-
Ownership period	-	-	-	-0,17	-0,06	-	-
Van fleet size	-	-	-	-	-	0,00	0,00

This trend is also observed in CAPEX and OPEX values for the different scenarios reflected in Figure 11. Additionally, if we compare the hydrogen generated with the purchase case, Figure 8 versus Figure 11, it can be

observed that scenarios S1G and S1P shows approximately the same per kilometer cost, this mean that for small annual hydrogen consumption, around 2,5 kgH₂ per van, it could be interesting to have an on-site hydrogen production infrastructure if the average hydrogen purchase price is over 4,2 €/kg.

Figure 11. Results for generated hydrogen case: total CAPEX, OPEX and per kilometer cost.

Nevertheless, in the hydrogen generated case, the scenarios where the BEV van type is the best option present a higher cost per kilometer compared to the equivalent scenario in hydrogen purchase case, where the FC-EREV were the preferred option. Figure 12 shows the cost per kilometer increment in percentage. The higher difference occurs with short ownership scenarios (5 years), high annual utilization (40.000 km), and bigger van fleets (320 vehicles). This means that, with the reference operational costs, the FC-EREV van option will be more economically advantageous as the fleet size and annual mileage increases, and the ownership period is reduced.

Figure 12. Cost per kilometer comparison: BEV versus FC-EREV van fleet.

Sensitive analysis.

The results are displayed in Table 21. The variation in the discount and inflation rate does not conduct to a change in the preferred van option but it causes the largest influence in per kilometer cost. On the other hand, the power term and electricity and gas cost reduction have also influence in the fleet operational cost but there is no change in the preferred van option. However, a 10% of increment in the acquisition or M&R costs of the FC powered van conducts to a change in the preferred van option to BEV type.

Table 21. Sensitive analysis results for generated hydrogen case.

	Unit	Variable value		Scenario results	
				S1G	
		Ref.	New	E ⁽¹⁾	PVO ⁽²⁾
Discount rate	(%)	2,5	6	-0,38	FCEREV
Inflation rate	(weight factor)	1	2,5	0,32	FCEREV
Average electricity price ⁽³⁾	(€/kWh)	0,168	0,151	0,04	FCEREV
Average CNG price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	2,695	2,425	0,11	FCEREV
FC van price ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,1	0,02	BEV
Power term price	(€/Kw year)	16,67	15,00	-0,03	FCEREV
FC van maintenance cost ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,1	0,03	BEV

Table captions: (1) E: elasticity value, (2) PVO: preferred van option, (3) Energy price is calculated as an average over the years considered in the study, (4) Under the denomination FC powered van are encompassed FCEV and FC-EREV types.

Breakeven analysis.

As seen in the previous section, the breakeven analysis is only conducted for the S1G scenario. Under this scenario conditions the economic factor breakeven points are listed in Table 22 and shows the following results:

- There is no electricity price low enough to change the van type selected, and FC-EREV van is the preferred option.
- The reduction in the CNG price breakeven value (1,7 €/kg) is similar to the hydrogen purchase case S1P.
- The increment in FC-EREV van purchase price must be less than 2% compared to the equivalent BEV van to remain as the best powertrain option. This breakeven value is approximately the same in the hydrogen purchase case scenario S1P.
- An increment over 9% in fuel cell vans maintenance cost conducts to become the BEV van as the best option. This is a 2% lower than the value calculated in the S1P scenario.

Table 22. Breakeven analysis results in generated hydrogen case.

	Unit	Variable base value	Scenario results	
			SIG	
			BP ⁽¹⁾	PVO ⁽²⁾
Average electricity price ⁽³⁾	(€/kWh)	0,168	NBP	FCEREV
Average CNG price ⁽³⁾	(€/kg)	2,695	1,70	CNG
FC van price ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,02	BEV
FC van maintenance cost ⁽⁴⁾	(weight factor)	1	1,09	BEV

Table captions: (1) BP: breaking point value of the variable analyzed, (2) PVO: preferred van option, (3) Energy price is calculated as an average over the years considered in the study, (4) Under the denomination FC powered van are encompassed FCEV and FC-EREV types, (5) NBP, means no break point value available because the value is too high or too low.

Summary of findings.

The results are valid for a large range of van fleet sizes, from 80 to 320 vehicles, and show that FC-EREV and BEV powertrain technologies are the best options to replace the CNG vans in most of the scenarios analyzed, but with low annual mileages (under 20.000 km) and short ownership periods (under 5 years) scenarios where the CNG price is lower than 1,7 €/kg, the CNG vans remains competitive. Nevertheless, pure FCEV vans have no room in last mile delivery fleets.

However, on-site hydrogen production using electricity from grid taken into account actual PEM hydrogen production technology is not competitive in the majority of the scenarios analyzed, and conducts to select the BEV van type as the preferred option. There is an exception, the scenario with low annual mileages. In this scenario the FC-EREV van fleets with annual mileages under 20.000 km and purchased hydrogen price over 4,2 €/kg becomes the on-site hydrogen generation using electricity from grid as a suitable option.

Therefore, the purchased hydrogen case is the most likely case. All the scenarios analyzed in this case results in a FC-EREV powertrain technology as the most suitable option when the economic variables have the reference values. However, a slightly increment in the FC-EREV purchase price, between 2 – 3%, become BEV van as the preferred option. A similar behavior is showed if the fuel cell powered van maintenance cost, with allowable increments in the 3% to 18% range depending on the annual mileage and the ownership period. Short ownership periods (5 years) and low utilization rates (20.000 km) makes possible higher increments in maintenance costs for FC-EREV vans. In case of electricity price behavior only if the ownership period is large enough (over 8 years), the annual distance is over 30.000 km and the electricity price is less than 0,11 €/kWh the BEV option would be of interest. On the other hand, the hydrogen price should be in the range of 6,5 to 13,2 €/kg in order to the FC-EREV van remains as the best option. The lowest hydrogen price corresponds to annual mileages of 40.000 km and 8 years of ownership period and the highest price with annual mileages of 30.000 km and 10 years of ownership.

CONCLUSIONS

The optimization tool provided in this study makes possible economic comparative calculations for different van types in the fleet replacement problem based on fleet operator requirements, such as annual mileage, ownership period and van fleet size, using different economic variables: discount and inflation rate, energy and power term costs, van purchase price and M&R costs. The algorithm outputs give information about CAPEX and OPEX costs for vans and its necessary infrastructure, cost savings with respect to the CNG initial van fleet, per kilometer costs, preferred van type option and the percentage of alternative vans in the total fleet over the time horizon under study. The linear programming optimization algorithm has been performed over a set of proposed scenarios. The scenario definition is based on three variables (yearly distance travelled, van ownership period and the size of the van fleet), and two hydrogen source pathways (purchased and on-site production). Additionally, the baseline scenario selected consists on a van fleet size of 200 vehicles with an average annual utilization of 30.000 km and an ownership period of 8 years. The results provided by the optimization algorithm were discussed performing a sensitive and a breakeven analysis.

It has been identified several operational fleet and economic variables that become FC-EREV vans as the preferred EV van option for fleet replacement problems:

- Average electricity price over 0,11 €/kWh
- Average hydrogen purchase price under 6,5 €/kg
- Average gas price over 1 €/kg.
- Van acquisition cost at most 2% higher than the equivalent BEV powered van.
- Van maintenance cost at most 3% higher than the equivalent BEV powered van.

Nevertheless, as it mentioned in the study there are other non-economic factors that affects to the purchase decision process and play in favor to FC-EREV due to the adaptation capability to unexpected usage patterns such as higher annual mileages or load capacity requirements for example.

The authors of this study have tried to provide an analysis tool to guide future investments in different van technologies in fleet replacement problems over a period of time for last-mile delivery purpose and asset the FC-EREV van as a suitable option for las mile delivery tasks. For future research it will be interesting to (1) include variables in the objective function to optimize environmental performances (GHG emissions) in operational conditions, (2) take into account variables in the objective function related to fast-charging infrastructure for BEV vans, and finally (3) consider electric auxiliary energy supply like solar to improve on-site green hydrogen production.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Oscar Castillo conceptualization, methodology, software and writing - original draft.

Roberto Alvarez conceptualization, methodology and performed writing - review and editing.

Appendix A.

International Electro-technical Commission (IEC) standard 62196 and 61851 defines requirements and tests for plugs, wiring connection to an AC/DC supply, and communication between the vehicle and the electrical vehicle supply equipment (EVSE). Basically there are four types of charging modes taken into account the vehicle inlet connector, charging electric current and power and the vehicle communication with the EVSE. In Table A1 are summarized the most usual charging modes in EU zone.

Table A1. Overview of charging modes (EVSE configurations) in EU zone.

Charge mode	Mode 1	Mode 2		Mode 3		Mode 4	
Charging type	Slow	Slow		Semi-fast		Fast	
Phases	1 AC	1 AC	3 AC	1 AC	3 AC	DC	
Max. current [A/phase]	10	≤ 16	≤ 32	≤ 32	≤ 64	≤ 125	≤ 200
Max. voltage [V]	250	250	480	250	480	≤ 850	≤ 500
Power output [kW]	≤ 2	≤ 7,4		3,7 – 7,4	3,7 – 43	50 – 125	
Plug	Schuko Type F (IEC 60884)	Schuko Type F (IEC 60884)	Mennekes Type 2 (IEC 62196-2)	Yazaki Type 1 (IEC 62196-2) (SAE J1772)	Mennekes Type 2 (IEC 62196-2)	CCS Combo2 (IEC 62196-3)	CHAdemo (JEVS G105-1993)
Number of pins	2	2	7	5	7	5	10
Description	Household socket with RCD protection	Household socket or charging cable has control box (IC-CPD) with control and safety functionalities		Specific socket on a dedicated circuit with extended control and safety functionalities		DC charging station with fixed charging cable	

Appendix B.

The CNG baseline price estimation is based on the IEA current policies natural gas cost estimation scenario proposed in the Heat Roadmap Europe report (Pietzcker et al., 2021) and it is adjusted using the Eurostat non-household gas prices from years 2015 to 2020 (Eurostat, 2022).

On the other hand, the reference scenario for electricity price is based on the average prices presented in the EU Reference Scenario 2020 (Deppermann et al., 2021) where it is supposed that the electricity price of the EU Member States will converge to a long-term average price.

In the case of hydrogen price estimation, the reference prices scenarios is based in an average price from different sources (Bloomberg NEF, 2020; Hydrogen Council, 2020; Vickers et al., 2020; Kakoulaki et al., 2021; Fuel Cells and Hydrogen Joint Undertaking, 2022) using the long term estimation of the Hydrogen Economy Outlook BNEF report (Bloomberg NEF, 2020).

Table B1. Reference energy cost evolution in € per kWh.

	Unit	2022	2023	2024	2025	2026	2027	2028	2029	2030	2031
CNG cost	€2021 /kg	2,05	2,11	2,17	2,23	2,29	2,35	2,41	2,47	2,53	2,57
Electricity cost	€2021 /kWh	0,163	0,163	0,164	0,165	0,166	0,166	0,167	0,168	0,169	0,169
H2 cost	€2021 /kg	6,59	6,29	5,98	5,67	5,34	5,01	4,67	4,32	3,96	3,93

	Unit	2032	2033	2034	2035	2036	2037	2038	2039	2040	2041
CNG cost	€2021 /kg	2,62	2,66	2,70	2,74	2,78	2,83	2,87	2,91	2,95	2,99
Electricity cost	€2021 /kWh	0,169	0,169	0,169	0,169	0,169	0,169	0,169	0,170	0,170	0,170
H2 cost	€2021 /kg	3,89	3,86	3,82	3,79	3,75	3,71	3,66	3,62	3,58	3,53

	Unit	2042	2043	2044	2045	2046	2047	2048	2049	2050
CNG cost	€2021 /kg	3,03	3,08	3,12	3,16	3,20	3,24	3,29	3,33	3,37
Electricity cost	€2021 /kWh	0,170	0,170	0,171	0,171	0,171	0,171	0,171	0,172	0,172
H2 cost	€2021 /kg	3,48	3,43	3,38	3,33	3,27	3,21	3,15	3,09	3,03

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